

ДИФФЕРЕНЦИРОВАНИЕ ЧЕТИРЕХМЕРНЫХ АЛГЕБР ЗИНБИЕЛЯ

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ABSTRACT

В этой статье мы рассчитываем матрицу D , используя таблицы умножения сложных разрешимых 4-мерных алгебр Зинбиеля. В основном, вычисляя таблицы умножения в теорема 1, мы получаем результаты.

1. Введение: В этой статье мы рассчитываем матрицу D , используя таблицы умножения сложных разрешимых 4-мерных алгебр Зинбиеля, заданных в теорема 1.

Для этого мы заменяем генеративные базисы $\{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4\}$ следующим образом

$$\begin{aligned} d(e_1) &= a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4, \\ d(e_2) &= b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4, \\ d(e_3) &= c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4, \\ d(e_4) &= p_1e_1 + p_2e_2 + p_3e_3 + p_4e_4, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

где $i, j, k, l \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, $a_i, b_j, c_k, p_l \in \mathbb{C}$. .. Далее, умножения разрешимых комплексных алгебр Зинбиеля вычисляем с помощью свойства дифференцирования следующим образом

$$d(e_i \circ e_j) = d(e_i) \circ e_j + e_i \circ d(e_j). \quad (2)$$

Основной результат в этой статье состоит в том, что, используя результаты (2), мы составляем следующую матрицу

$$D = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & b_1 & c_1 & p_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 & c_2 & p_2 \\ a_3 & b_3 & c_3 & p_3 \\ a_4 & b_4 & c_4 & p_4 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

2. Основная часть

Теорема 1. Любая 4-мерная комплексная не разложимая алгебра Зинбиеля изоморфна одной из следующих попарно неизоморфных алгебр:

$$A_1 : e_1 \circ e_1 = e_2, e_1 \circ e_2 = e_3, e_2 \circ e_1 = 2e_3, \quad d(e_1) = a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4,$$

$$e_1 \circ e_3 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_2 = 3e_4, e_3 \circ e_1 = 3e_4. \quad d(e_2) = b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4.$$

$$d(e_2) = d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) =$$

$$= a_1e_2 + 2a_2e_3 + 3a_3e_4 + a_1e_2 + a_2e_3 + a_3e_4 = 2a_1e_2 + 3a_2e_3 + 4a_3e_4,$$

$$b_1 = 0,$$

$$b_2 = 2a_1,$$

$$b_3 = 3a_2,$$

$$b_4 = 4a_3.$$

$$d(e_2) = 2a_1e_2 + 3a_2e_3 + 4a_3e_4.$$

$$d(e_3) = d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (2a_1e_2 + 3a_2e_3 + 4a_3e_4) =$$

$$= a_1e_3 + 3a_2e_4 + 2a_1e_3 + 3a_2e_4 = 3a_1e_3 + 6a_2e_4,$$

$$d(e_3) = \frac{1}{2}d(e_2 \circ e_1) = \frac{1}{2}(d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1)) = \frac{1}{2}((2a_1e_2 + 3a_2e_3 + 4a_3e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 +$$

$$+ a_4e_4)) = \frac{1}{2}(4a_1e_3 + 9a_2e_4 + 2a_1e_3 + 3a_2e_4) = \frac{1}{2}(6a_1e_3 + 12a_2e_4) = 3a_1e_3 + 6a_2e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_1 \circ e_3) = d(e_1) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ d(e_3) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ (3a_1e_3 + 6a_2e_4) =$$

$$= a_1e_4 + 3a_1e_4 = 4a_1e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = \frac{1}{3}d(e_2 \circ e_2) = \frac{1}{3}(d(e_2) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ d(e_2)) = \frac{1}{3}((2a_1e_2 + 3a_2e_3 + 4a_3e_4) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ (2a_1e_2 + 3a_2e_3 +$$

$$+ 4a_3e_4)) = \frac{1}{3}(6a_1e_4 + 6a_1e_4) = \frac{1}{3} 12a_1e_4 = 4a_1e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = \frac{1}{3}d(e_3 \circ e_1) = \frac{1}{3}(d(e_3) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ d(e_1)) = \frac{1}{3}((3a_1e_3 + 6a_2e_4) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4)) =$$

$$= \frac{1}{3}(9a_1e_4 + 3a_1e_4) = \frac{1}{3} 12a_1e_4 = 4a_1e_4.$$

$$A_2 : e_1 \circ e_1 = e_2, e_1 \circ e_2 = e_4, e_1 \circ e_3 = e_4, e_3 \circ e_1 = 2e_4. \quad d(e_1) = a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4,$$

$$d(e_2) = b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4.$$

$$d(e_3) = d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) =$$

$$= a_1e_3 + 2a_2e_4 + a_1e_3 + a_2e_4 + a_3e_4 = 2a_1e_3 + (3a_3 + a_2)e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_1 \circ e_3) = d(e_1) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ d(e_3) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ (2a_1e_3 + a_2e_4 + 3a_3e_4) =$$

$$= a_1e_4 + 2a_1e_4 = 3a_1e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) =$$

$$= a_1e_4 + b_1e_3 + b_2e_4 + b_3e_4 = b_1e_3 + (a_1 + b_2 + b_3)e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = \frac{1}{2}d(e_3 \circ e_1) = \frac{1}{2}(d(e_3) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ d(e_1)) = \frac{1}{2}(2a_1e_3 + (a_2 + 3a_3)e_4) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 +$$

$$+ a_4e_4) = \frac{1}{2}(4a_1e_4 + 2a_1e_4) = \frac{1}{2} 6a_1e_4 = 3a_1e_4.$$

$$b_1 = 0,$$

$$b_1 = 0,$$

$$a_1 + b_2 + b_3 = 3a_1.$$

$$b_2 + b_3 = 2a_1.$$

$$d(e_4) = 3a_1e_4.$$

$$e_2 \circ e_1 = 0. \quad d(e_2 \circ e_1) = d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1) = (b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = \\ = 2b_3e_4 = 0 \quad b_3 = 0.$$

$$A_3 : e_1 \circ e_1 = e_3, e_1 \circ e_3 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_2 = e_4, e_3 \circ e_1 = 2e_4. \quad d(e_1) = a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4, \\ d(e_2) = b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4. \\ d(e_3) = d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = \\ = a_1e_3 + 2a_3e_4 + a_1e_3 + a_3e_4 = 2a_1e_3 + 3a_3e_4, \\ d(e_4) = d(e_1 \circ e_3) = d(e_1) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ d(e_3) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ (2a_1e_3 + a_2e_4 + 3a_3e_4) = \\ = a_1e_4 + 2a_1e_4 = 3a_1e_4, \\ d(e_4) = d(e_2 \circ e_2) = d(e_2) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ d(e_2) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = \\ = b_2e_4 + b_2e_4 = 2b_2e_4, \\ d(e_4) = \frac{1}{2}d(e_3 \circ e_1) = \frac{1}{2}(d(e_3) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ d(e_1)) = \frac{1}{2}((2a_1e_3 + 3a_3e_4) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4)) = \\ = \frac{1}{2}(4a_1e_4 + 2a_1e_4) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 6a_1e_4 = 3a_1e_4. \\ 2b_2 = 3a_1. \quad b_2 = \frac{3}{2}a_1. \quad d(e_4) = 3a_1e_4. \\ e_1 \circ e_2 = 0. \quad d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + \\ + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = a_2e_4 + b_1e_3 + b_3e_4 = b_1e_3 + (a_2 + b_3)e_4 = 0. \quad b_1 = 0, \\ b_3 = -a_2.$$

$$A_4 : e_1 \circ e_2 = e_3, e_1 \circ e_3 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_1 = -e_3. \quad d(e_1) = a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4, \\ d(e_2) = b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4. \\ d(e_3) = d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = \\ = a_1e_3 + b_2e_3 + b_3e_4 = (a_1 + b_2)e_3 + b_3e_4, \\ d(e_3) = -d(e_2 \circ e_1) = -(d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1)) = -((b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + \\ + a_4e_4)) = -b_2e_3 - a_1e_3 = -(a_1 + b_2)e_3, \\ a_1 + b_2 = -a_1 - b_2, \quad b_2 = -a_1, \quad d(e_3) = 0. \\ b_3 = 0. \quad b_3 = 0. \\ d(e_4) = d(e_1 \circ e_3) = d(e_1) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ d(e_3) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ 0 = a_1e_4, \\ e_1 \circ e_1 = 0, \quad d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + \\ + a_4e_4) = -a_2e_3 + a_3e_4 + a_2e_3 = a_3e_4 = 0. \quad a_3 = 0, \\ e_2 \circ e_3 = 0, \quad d(e_2 \circ e_3) = d(e_2) \circ e_3 + e_2 \circ d(e_3) = (b_1e_1 + 2a_1e_2 - 2a_2e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_2 \circ 0 = b_1e_4 = 0. \\ b_1 = 0.$$

$$A_5 : e_1 \circ e_2 = e_3, e_1 \circ e_3 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_1 = -e_3, e_2 \circ e_2 = e_4. \quad d(e_1) = a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4, \\ d(e_2) = b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4. \\ d(e_3) = d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = \\ = a_1e_3 + a_2e_4 + b_2e_3 + b_3e_4 = (a_1 + b_2)e_3 + (a_2 + b_3)e_4,$$

$$d(e_3) = -d(e_2 \circ e_1) = -(d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1)) = -((b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4)) = b_2e_3 + a_1e_3 - a_2e_4 = (a_1 + b_2)e_3 - a_2e_4,$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 + b_2 &= a_1 + b_2, & b_3 &= -2a_2. & d(e_3) &= (a_1 + b_2)e_3 - a_2e_4 \\ b_3 + a_2 &= -a_2. \end{aligned}$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_1 \circ e_3) = d(e_1) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ d(e_3) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ ((a_1 + b_2)e_3 - a_2e_4) = a_1e_4 + (a_1 + b_2)e_4 = (2a_1 + b_2)e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_2 \circ e_2) = d(e_2) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ d(e_2) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 - 2a_2e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 - 2a_2e_3 + b_4e_4) = b_1e_3 + b_2e_4 - b_1e_3 + b_2e_4 = 2b_2e_4,$$

$$2a_1 + b_2 = 2b_2. \quad b_2 = 2a_1. \quad d(e_4) = 4a_1e_4.$$

$$e_1 \circ e_1 = 0, \quad d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = a_2e_3 + a_3e_4 - a_2e_3 = a_3e_4 = 0. \quad a_3 = 0,$$

$$e_2 \circ e_3 = 0, \quad d(e_2 \circ e_3) = d(e_2) \circ e_3 + e_2 \circ d(e_3) = (b_1e_1 + 2a_1e_2 - 2a_2e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_2 \circ ((a_1 + b_2)e_3 - a_2e_4) = b_1e_4 = 0. \quad b_1 = 0.$$

$$A_6 : e_1 \circ e_1 = e_4, e_1 \circ e_2 = e_3, e_2 \circ e_1 = -e_3, e_2 \circ e_2 = -2e_3 + e_4. \quad \begin{aligned} d(e_1) &= a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4, \\ d(e_2) &= b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4. \end{aligned}$$

$$d(e_3) = d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = a_1e_3 - 2a_2e_3 + a_2e_4 + b_1e_4 + b_1e_3 = (a_1 - 2a_2 + b_2)e_3 - (a_2 + b_1)e_4,$$

$$d(e_3) = -d(e_2 \circ e_1) = -(d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1)) = -((b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4)) = -(b_1e_4 - b_2e_3 - a_1e_3 - 2a_2e_3 + a_2e_4) = (a_1 + 2a_2 + b_2)e_3 - (a_2 + b_1)e_4,$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 - 2a_2 + b_2 &= a_1 + 2a_2 + b_2, & 4a_2 &= 0, & a_2 &= 0, \\ a_2 + b_1 &= -a_2 - b_1. & b_1 &= -a_2. & b_1 &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad d(e_3) = (a_1 + b_2)e_3.$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = a_1e_4 + a_1e_4 = 2a_1e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_2 \circ e_2 + 2e_3) = d(e_2 \circ e_2) + 2d(e_3) = d(e_2) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ d(e_2) + 2d(e_3) = (b_2e_2 + b_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ (b_2e_2 + b_4e_4) + 2(a_1 + b_2)e_3 = -2b_2e_3 + b_2e_4 - 2b_2e_3 + b_2e_4 + 2a_1e_3 + 2b_2e_3 = 2a_1e_3 - 2b_2e_3 + 2b_2e_4 = (2a_1 - 2b_2)e_3 + 2b_2e_4,$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2a_1 - 2b_2 &= 0, & b_2 &= a_1. & d(e_4) &= 2a_1e_4. \\ 2b_2 &= 2a_1. \end{aligned}$$

$$A_7 : e_1 \circ e_2 = e_3, e_2 \circ e_1 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_2 = -e_3. \quad \begin{aligned} d(e_1) &= a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4, \\ d(e_2) &= b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4. \end{aligned}$$

$$d(e_3) = d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = a_1e_3 - a_2e_3 + b_2e_3 = (a_1 - a_2 + b_2)e_3,$$

$$d(e_3) = -d(e_2 \circ e_2) = -(d(e_2) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ d(e_2)) = -((b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4)) = -(b_1e_3 - b_2e_3 + b_1e_4 - b_2e_3) = (-b_1 + 2b_2)e_3 - b_1e_4,$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 - a_2 + b_2 &= -b_1 + 2b_2, & b_2 &= a_1 - a_2, \\ -b_1 &= 0. & b_1 &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad d(e_3) = 2(a_1 - a_2)e_3.$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(e_4) &= d(e_2 \circ e_1) = d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1) = (b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = \\ &= b_2e_4 + a_1e_4 - a_2e_3 = -a_2e_3 + (a_1 + b_2)e_4 = -a_2e_3 + (2a_1 - a_2)e_4, \\ e_1 \circ e_1 &= 0, \quad d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + \\ &+ a_4e_4) = a_2e_4 + a_2e_3 = 0. \quad a_2 = 0. \quad b_2 = a_1. \quad d(e_3) = 2a_1e_3, \\ & \quad \quad \quad d(e_4) = 2a_1e_4. \end{aligned}$$

$$A_8(\alpha) : e_1 \circ e_1 = e_3, e_1 \circ e_2 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_1 = -\alpha e_3, e_2 \circ e_2 = -e_4, \alpha \quad \begin{aligned} d(e_1) &= a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4, \\ d(e_2) &= b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(e_3) &= -\frac{1}{\alpha}d(e_2 \circ e_1) = -\frac{1}{\alpha}(d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1)) = -\frac{1}{\alpha}((b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + \\ &+ a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4)) = -\frac{1}{\alpha}(b_1e_3 - \alpha b_2e_3 - \alpha a_1e_3 - a_2e_4) = (-\frac{1}{\alpha}b_1 + b_2 + a_1)e_3 + \frac{1}{\alpha}a_2e_4, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(e_3) &= d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = \\ &= a_1e_3 - \alpha a_2e_3 + a_1e_3 + a_2e_4 = (2a_1 - \alpha a_2)e_3 + a_2e_4, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\alpha}a_2 &= a_2, & \alpha &= 1, & d(e_3) &= (2a_1 - a_2)e_3 + a_2e_4. \\ -\frac{1}{\alpha}b_1 + b_2 + a_1 &= 2a_1 - \alpha a_2. & b_2 &= a_1 - a_2 + b_1. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(e_4) &= d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = \\ &= a_1e_4 - a_2e_4 + b_1e_3 + b_2e_4 = b_1e_3 + (a_1 - a_2 + b_2)e_4, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(e_4) &= -d(e_2 \circ e_2) = -(d(e_2) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ d(e_2)) = -((b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + \\ &+ b_4e_4)) = b_1e_3 + b_2e_4 - b_1e_4 + b_2e_4 = b_1e_3 + (-b_1 + 2b_2)e_4, \end{aligned}$$

$$d(e_4) = b_1e_3 + (2a_1 - 2a_2 + b_1)e_4.$$

$$A_9(\alpha) : e_1 \circ e_1 = e_4, e_1 \circ e_2 = \alpha e_4, e_2 \circ e_1 = -\alpha e_4, \quad \begin{aligned} d(e_1) &= a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4, \\ e_2 \circ e_2 &= e_4, e_3 \circ e_3 = e_4, \alpha \quad \begin{aligned} d(e_2) &= b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4, \\ d(e_3) &= c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4. \end{aligned} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(e_4) &= d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = \\ &= a_1e_4 - \alpha a_2e_4 + a_1e_4 + \alpha a_2e_4 = 2a_1e_4. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(e_4) &= \frac{1}{\alpha}d(e_1 \circ e_2) = \frac{1}{\alpha}(d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2)) = \frac{1}{\alpha}((a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + \\ &+ b_3e_3 + b_4e_4)) = \frac{1}{\alpha}(a_1e_4 + a_2e_4 + b_1e_4 + \alpha b_2e_4) = (a_1 + \frac{1}{\alpha}a_2 + \frac{1}{\alpha}b_1 + b_2)e_4, \end{aligned}$$

$$d(e_4) = -\frac{1}{\alpha}d(e_2 \circ e_1) = -\frac{1}{\alpha}(d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1)) = -\frac{1}{\alpha}((b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ$$

$$\circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4)) = -\frac{1}{\alpha}(b_1e_4 - \alpha b_2e_4 - \alpha a_1e_4 + a_2e_4) = (a_1 - \frac{1}{\alpha}a_2 - \frac{1}{\alpha}b_1 + b_2)e_4,$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(e_4) &= d(e_2 \circ e_2) = d(e_2) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ d(e_2) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = \\ &= \alpha b_1e_4 + b_2e_4 - \alpha b_1e_4 + b_2e_4 = 2b_2e_4, \end{aligned}$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_3 \circ e_3) = d(e_3) \circ e_3 + e_3 \circ d(e_3) = (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_3 \circ (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) = \\ = c_3e_4 + c_3e_4 = 2c_3e_4.$$

$$2b_2 = 2c_3 = 2a_1,$$

$$c_3 = b_2 = a_1,$$

$$a_1 + \frac{1}{\alpha}a_2 + \frac{1}{\alpha}b_1 + b_2 = a_1 - \frac{1}{\alpha}a_2 - \frac{1}{\alpha}b_1 + b_2. \quad b_1 = -a_2.$$

$$e_1 \circ e_3 = 0, \quad d(e_1 \circ e_3) = d(e_1) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ d(e_3) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + \\ + c_4e_4) = a_3e_4 + c_1e_4 + \alpha c_2e_4 = (a_3 + c_1 + \alpha c_2)e_4 = 0. \quad c_2 = \frac{1}{\alpha}(a_3 + c_1).$$

$$e_3 \circ e_1 = 0, \quad d(e_3 \circ e_1) = d(e_3) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ d(e_1) = (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + \\ + a_4e_4) = c_1e_4 - \alpha c_2e_4 + a_3e_4 = (a_3 + c_1 - \alpha c_2)e_4 = 0. \quad c_2 = \frac{1}{\alpha}(a_3 + c_1). \quad -a_3 - c_1 = a_3 + c_1. \quad \begin{matrix} c_1 = -a_3, \\ c_2 = 0. \end{matrix}$$

$$e_2 \circ e_3 = 0, \quad d(e_2 \circ e_3) = d(e_2) \circ e_3 + e_2 \circ d(e_3) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_2 \circ (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + \\ + c_4e_4) = b_3e_4 - \alpha c_1e_4 + c_2e_4 = (b_3 - \alpha c_1 + c_2)e_4 = 0. \quad c_2 = -b_3 + \alpha c_1.$$

$$e_3 \circ e_2 = 0, \quad d(e_3 \circ e_2) = d(e_3) \circ e_2 + e_3 \circ d(e_2) = (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_3 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + \\ + b_4e_4) = \alpha c_1e_4 + c_2e_4 + b_3e_4 = (\alpha c_1 + c_2 + b_3)e_4 = 0. \quad c_2 = -b_3 - \alpha c_1. \quad -b_3 - \alpha c_1 = -b_3 + \alpha c_1. \quad \begin{matrix} c_1 = 0, \\ b_3 = 0. \end{matrix}$$

$$e_3 \circ e_3 = 0, \quad d(e_3 \circ e_3) = d(e_3) \circ e_3 + e_3 \circ d(e_3) = (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_3 \circ (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + \\ + c_4e_4) = c_3e_4 + c_3e_4 = 2c_3e_4 = 0. \quad c_3 = 0. \quad \begin{matrix} b_2 = 0, \\ a_1 = 0. \end{matrix} \quad d(e_4) = 0.$$

$$d(e_1) = a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4,$$

$$A_{10} : e_1 \circ e_2 = e_4, e_1 \circ e_3 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_1 = -e_4, e_2 \circ e_2 = e_4, e_3 \circ e_1 = e_4. \quad d(e_2) = b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4,$$

$$d(e_3) = c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4.$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = \\ = a_1e_4 + a_2e_4 + b_2e_4 + b_3e_4 = (a_1 + a_2 + b_2 + b_3)e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_1 \circ e_3) = d(e_1) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ d(e_3) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) = \\ = a_1e_4 + c_2e_4 + a_3e_4 = (a_1 + a_3 + c_2)e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = -d(e_2 \circ e_1) = -(d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1)) = -((b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + \\ + a_4e_4)) = b_2e_4 - b_3e_4 + a_1e_4 - a_2e_4 = (a_1 - a_2 + b_2 - b_3)e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_2 \circ e_2) = d(e_2) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ d(e_2) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = \\ = b_1e_4 + b_2e_4 - b_1e_4 + b_2e_4 = 2b_2e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_3 \circ e_1) = d(e_3) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ d(e_1) = (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = \\ = -c_2e_4 + c_3e_4 + a_1e_4 = (a_1 - c_2 + c_3)e_4.$$

$$a_1 + a_2 + b_2 + b_3 = a_1 - a_2 + b_2 - b_3,$$

$$b_3 = -a_2,$$

$$a_1 + a_2 + b_2 + b_3 = 2b_2,$$

$$b_2 = a_1,$$

$$d(e_4) = 2a_1e_4.$$

$$a_1 + a_3 + c_2 = a_1 - c_2 + c_3.$$

$$c_3 = a_3 + 2c_2.$$

$$e_1 \circ e_1 = 0, \quad d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = -a_2e_4 + a_3e_4 + a_2e_4 + a_3e_4 = 2a_3e_4 = 0. \quad a_3 = 0. \quad c_3 = 2c_2.$$

$$e_2 \circ e_3 = 0, \quad d(e_2 \circ e_3) = d(e_2) \circ e_3 + e_2 \circ d(e_3) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_2 \circ (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) = b_1e_4 - c_1e_4 + c_2e_4 = (b_1 - c_1 + c_2)e_4 = 0. \quad c_2 = -b_1 + c_1. \quad c_3 = -2b_1 + 2c_1.$$

$$e_3 \circ e_3 = 0, \quad d(e_3 \circ e_3) = d(e_3) \circ e_3 + e_3 \circ d(e_3) = (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_3 \circ (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) = c_1e_4 + c_1e_4 = 2c_1e_4 = 0. \quad c_1 = 0. \quad c_2 = -b_1, \quad c_3 = -2b_1.$$

$$d(e_1) = a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4,$$

$$A_{11} : e_1 \circ e_1 = e_4, e_1 \circ e_2 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_1 = -e_4, e_3 \circ e_3 = e_4. \quad d(e_2) = b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4,$$

$$d(e_3) = c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4.$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = a_1e_4 - a_2e_4 + a_1e_4 + a_2e_4 = 2a_1e_4.$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = a_1e_4 + b_1e_4 + b_2e_4 = (a_1 + b_1 + b_2)e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = -d(e_2 \circ e_1) = -(d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1)) = -((b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4)) = -(b_1e_4 - b_2e_4 - a_1e_4) = a_1e_4 - b_1e_4 + b_2e_4 = (a_1 - b_1 + b_2)e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_3 \circ e_3) = d(e_3) \circ e_3 + e_3 \circ d(e_3) = (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_3 \circ (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) = c_3e_4 + c_3e_4 = 2c_3e_4.$$

$$a_1 + b_1 + b_2 = a_1 - b_1 + b_2, \quad b_1 = 0, \quad d(e_4) = 2a_2e_4. \\ 2a_2 = 3a_3. \quad c_3 = a_2.$$

$$e_1 \circ e_3 = 0, \quad d(e_1 \circ e_3) = d(e_1) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ d(e_3) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) = a_3e_4 + c_1e_4 + c_2e_4 = (a_3 + c_1 + c_2)e_4 = 0. \quad c_2 = -a_3 - c_1.$$

$$e_3 \circ e_1 = 0, \quad d(e_3 \circ e_1) = d(e_3) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ d(e_1) = (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = c_1e_4 - c_2e_4 + a_3e_4 = (a_3 + c_1 - c_2)e_4 = 0. \quad c_2 = a_3 + c_1. \quad -a_3 - c_1 = a_3 + c_1. \quad c_1 = -a_3, \quad c_2 = 0.$$

$$e_3 \circ e_2 = 0, \quad d(e_3 \circ e_2) = d(e_3) \circ e_2 + e_3 \circ d(e_2) = (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_3 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = c_1e_4 + b_3e_4 = (c_1 + b_3)e_4 = 0. \quad c_1 = -b_3, \quad b_3 = a_3.$$

$$d(e_1) = a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4,$$

$$A_{12} : e_1 \circ e_2 = e_3, e_2 \circ e_1 = e_4. \quad d(e_2) = b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4.$$

$$d(e_3) = d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = a_1e_3 + b_2e_3 = (a_1 + b_2)e_3,$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_2 \circ e_1) = d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = b_2e_4 + a_1e_4 = (a_1 + b_2)e_4,$$

$$e_1 \circ e_1 = 0, \quad d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = a_2e_4 + a_2e_3. \quad a_2 = 0.$$

$$e_2 \circ e_2 = 0. \quad d(e_2 \circ e_2) = d(e_2) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ d(e_2) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = b_1e_3 + b_1e_4 = 0. \quad b_1 = 0.$$

$$A_{13} : e_1 \circ e_2 = e_3, e_2 \circ e_1 = -e_3, e_2 \circ e_2 = e_4. \quad \begin{aligned} d(e_1) &= a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4, \\ d(e_2) &= b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4. \end{aligned}$$

$$d(e_3) = d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = a_1e_3 + a_2e_4 + b_2e_3 = (a_1 + b_2)e_3 + a_2e_4,$$

$$d(e_3) = -d(e_2 \circ e_1) = -(d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1)) = -((b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4)) = -(-b_2e_3 - a_1e_3 + a_2e_4) = (a_1 + b_2)e_3 - a_2e_4,$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 + b_2 &= a_1 + b_2, \\ a_2 &= -a_2. \end{aligned} \quad a_2 = 0. \quad d(e_3) = (a_1 + b_2)e_3.$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_2 \circ e_2) = d(e_2) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ d(e_2) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = b_1e_3 + b_2e_4 - b_1e_3 + b_2e_4 = 2b_2e_4.$$

$$A_{14} : e_2 \circ e_1 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_2 = e_3. \quad \begin{aligned} d(e_1) &= a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4, \\ d(e_2) &= b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4. \end{aligned}$$

$$d(e_3) = d(e_2 \circ e_2) = d(e_2) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ d(e_2) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = b_2e_3 + b_1e_4 + b_2e_3 = 2b_2e_3 + b_1e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_2 \circ e_1) = d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = b_2e_4 + a_1e_4 + a_2e_3 = a_2e_3 + (a_1 + b_2)e_4,$$

$$e_1 \circ e_1 = 0, \quad d(e_1 \circ e_1) = d(e_1) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ d(e_1) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_1 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = a_2e_4 + a_2e_4 = 2a_2e_4 = 0. \quad a_2 = 0.$$

$$A_{15}(\alpha) : e_1 \circ e_2 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_2 = e_3, e_2 \circ e_1 = \frac{1+\alpha}{1-\alpha}e_4, \alpha \in \{1\}. \quad \begin{aligned} d(e_1) &= a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4, \\ d(e_2) &= b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4. \end{aligned}$$

$$d(e_3) = d(e_2 \circ e_2) = d(e_2) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ d(e_2) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_2 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = b_1e_4 + b_2e_3 + \frac{1+\alpha}{1-\alpha}b_1e_4 + b_2e_3 = 2b_2e_3 + \frac{2}{1-\alpha}b_1e_4,$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = a_1e_4 + a_2e_3 + b_2e_4 = a_2e_3 + (a_1 + b_2)e_4,$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1+\alpha}{1-\alpha}d(e_4) &= d(e_2 \circ e_1) = d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = \\ &= \frac{1+\alpha}{1-\alpha}b_2e_4 + \frac{1+\alpha}{1-\alpha}a_1e_4 + a_2e_3 = a_2e_3 + \frac{1+\alpha}{1-\alpha}(a_1 + b_2)e_4. \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{1+\alpha}{1-\alpha}(a_2e_3 + (a_1 + b_2)e_4) = a_2e_3 + \frac{1+\alpha}{1-\alpha}(a_1 + b_2)e_4 \quad a_2 = \frac{1+\alpha}{1-\alpha}a_2,$$

$$\frac{1+\alpha}{1-\alpha}(a_1 + b_2) = \frac{1+\alpha}{1-\alpha}(a_1 + b_2).$$

$$\frac{1+\alpha}{1-\alpha} + 1 \quad a_2 \quad \frac{2\alpha}{1-\alpha}a_2 \quad \alpha = 0, \quad \alpha = 0, \forall a_2, \quad d(a_4) = 2a_2e_4.$$

$$\alpha a_2 = 0. \quad \alpha = 0, a_2 = 0.$$

$$d(e_1) = a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4,$$

$$A_{16} : e_1 \circ e_2 = e_4, e_2 \circ e_1 = -e_4, e_3 \circ e_3 = e_4. \quad d(e_2) = b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4,$$

$$d(e_3) = c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4.$$

$$d(e_4) = -d(e_1 \circ e_2) = d(e_1) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ d(e_2) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_1 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = a_1e_4 + b_2e_4 = (a_1 + b_2)e_4.$$

$$d(e_4) = -d(e_2 \circ e_1) = -(d(e_2) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ d(e_1)) = -((b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_2 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4)) = -(b_2e_4 + a_1e_4) = -(a_1 + b_2)e_4.$$

$$d(e_4) = d(e_3 \circ e_3) = d(e_3) \circ e_3 + e_3 \circ d(e_3) = (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_3 \circ (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) = c_3e_4 + c_3e_4 = 2c_3e_4.$$

$$a_1 + b_2 = -a_1 - b_2, \quad b_2 = -a_1, \quad d(e_4) = 0.$$

$$a_1 + b_2 = 2c_3. \quad c_3 = 0.$$

$$e_1 \circ e_3 = 0, \quad d(e_1 \circ e_3) = d(e_1) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ d(e_3) = (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_1 \circ (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) = a_3e_4 + c_2e_4 = (a_3 + c_2)e_4 = 0. \quad c_2 = -a_3.$$

$$e_2 \circ e_3 = 0, \quad d(e_2 \circ e_3) = d(e_2) \circ e_3 + e_2 \circ d(e_3) = (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) \circ e_3 + e_2 \circ (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) = b_3e_4 - c_1e_4 = (b_3 - c_1)e_4 = 0. \quad c_1 = b_3.$$

$$e_3 \circ e_1 = 0, \quad d(e_3 \circ e_1) = d(e_3) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ d(e_1) = (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) \circ e_1 + e_3 \circ (a_1e_1 + a_2e_2 + a_3e_3 + a_4e_4) = -c_2e_4 + a_3e_4 = (a_3 - c_2)e_4 = 0. \quad c_2 = a_3. \quad a_3 = -a_3$$

$$c_2 = 0.$$

$$e_3 \circ e_2 = 0, \quad d(e_3 \circ e_2) = d(e_3) \circ e_2 + e_3 \circ d(e_2) = (c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + c_3e_3 + c_4e_4) \circ e_2 + e_3 \circ (b_1e_1 + b_2e_2 + b_3e_3 + b_4e_4) = c_1e_4 + b_3e_4 = (c_1 + b_3)e_4 = 0. \quad c_1 = -b_3. \quad b_3 = -b_3$$

$$b_3 = 0, \quad c_1 = 0.$$

$$D_1 = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & 2a_1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_3 & 3a_2 & 3a_1 & 0 \\ a_4 & 4a_3 & 6a_2 & 4a_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_2 = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & b_2 & 0 & 0 \\ a_3 & 0 & 2a_1 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & 3a_3 + a_2 & 3a_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_3 = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & \frac{3}{2}a_1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_3 & -a_2 & 3a_1 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & 3a_3 & 3a_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_4 = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & -a_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & 0 & a_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_5 = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & 2a_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -2a_2 & a_1 + b_2 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & -a_2 & 4a_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_6 = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_3 & b_3 & a_1 + b_2 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & 0 & 2a_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_7 = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_3 & b_3 & 2a_1 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & 0 & 2a_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_8 = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & b_1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & a_1 - a_2 + b_1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_3 & b_3 & 2a_1 - a_2 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & a_2 & 2a_1 - 2a_2 + b_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ b_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 2a_1 - 2a_2 + b_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_9 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -a_2 & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & c_4 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_{10} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & b_1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & a_1 & -b_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -a_2 & -2b_1 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & c_4 & 2a_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_{11} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 & -a_3 & 0 \\ a_2 & b_2 & 0 & 0 \\ a_3 & a_3 & a_2 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & c_4 & 2a_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_{12} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & b_2 & 0 & 0 \\ a_3 & b_3 & a_1 + b_2 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & 0 & a_1 + b_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_{13} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & b_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & b_2 & 0 & 0 \\ a_3 & b_3 & a_1 + b_2 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & 0 & 2b_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_{14} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & b_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & b_2 & 0 & 0 \\ a_3 & b_3 & 2b_2 & a_2 \\ a_4 & b_4 & b_1 & a_1 + b_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_{15} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & b_1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & b_2 & 0 & 0 \\ a_3 & b_3 & 2b_2 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & \frac{2}{1-\alpha}b_1 & 2a_1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{cases} \alpha = 0, \forall a_2 \\ \alpha = 0, a_2 = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$D_{16} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & b_1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & -a_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_4 & b_4 & c_4 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Мы вычислили все случаи умножения разрешимых комплексных алгебр Зинбиеля и не написали лишних решений.

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